

Nurse's Perceived on the Head Nurse Organizational Culture in Inpatient Room of Banda Aceh Hospital

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Abstract:

Organizational culture is a characteristic of an organization related to nurses' good and bad performances. The lousy performance of nurses will impact the services provided. This research aims to determine the perception of head nurses about organizational culture in the inpatient room at Banda Aceh Hospital. The research design used in this research was descriptive quantitative with a cross-sectional study approach. It was conducted in Banda Aceh Hospital. The sample in this research was 60 respondents using the total sampling technique. The data was collected by distributing questionnaires to the head of the inpatient room. The analysis used in this study was univariate. The results showed that the nurses' perceptions of the organizational culture in the Banda Aceh hospital inpatient room were in a good category, i.e., 37 respondents (61.7%). In the involvement sub variable, 41 respondents (61.7%) indicated good involvement, 39 respondents (65.0%) showed good consistency, 42 respondents (70.0%), and 37 respondents (61.7%) showed good mission. From the results, it is hoped that the head of the room will continue to improve the organizational culture in the hospital because it will affect the performance of the head nurse.

Keywords: Involvement, Consistency, Adjustment, Organizational Mission,

IJMNHS

Accepted 27 December 2021
Published 30 December 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5810351

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Introduction

Hospital is a health service institution that serves individual health services by providing inpatient, outpatient, and emergency care services (Permenkes RI, 2020). Nursing services as an integral part of health services significantly contribute to determining the quality of hospitals. Therefore, all health service providers in hospitals, including nurses, must have knowledge and skills that continue to develop along with technological developments in the health sector (Fadhila & Afriani, 2020).

Nurses are the most crucial resource in hospitals from the dominant number (55-65%) and provide comprehensive and professional health services to patients consistently and continuously for 24 hours (Simamora et al., 2017). In improving the quality of nursing care services, each hospital has an organizational culture as a reference and guidance for nurses in carrying out their duties.

Organizational culture is a system of values shared by all organization members. It functions as a binding for all components of the organization. It can also be used as guidance in creating the attitudes and behavior of nurses and facilitates the sense of commitment at work. Hospital organizational culture is a guideline or reference for controlling organizational behavior, nurses' behavior, and other health teams in interacting to achieve organizational goals (Sari, 2019).

In a study on the strength of organizational culture with the professionalism of nurses, it was found that a solid organizational culture had an impact on the excellent performance of nurses (Apriyatmoko & Susilo, 2014). Denison emphasizes four dimensions for an organizational culture that must be mastered to run effectively. The four dimensions in the Denison model are mission, adaptability, involvement, and consistency (Ariani, 2016).

Based on the description, the researcher is interested in researching the perception of head nurses about organizational culture in the inpatient room at Banda Aceh Hospital.

Methodology

This study, based on a descriptive quantitative plan and a cross-sectional approach, was conducted in a hospitalization room of the Banda Aceh hospital. The population size of the study was 70. The sampling technique used was the total sampling method, and the respondents in this study were 60 therefore, the response rate is 85.71%.

This study uses a significance level of 5%. The questionnaire consists of 32 statement items. This research has been tested for validity, and the results obtained with the calculated r-value above the r table value (0,514) and reliability test with Cronbach's Alpha value 0, 75. The review board conducted the ethical consideration from the Faculty of Nursing, Universitas Syiah Kuala (FON-USK). Its review considers six aspects: autonomy, beneficence, justice, nonmaleficence, veracity, and confidentiality. Data collection was carried out from September 30th to October 13th, 2021, by distributing questionnaires with 32 questions to respondents. The

questionnaire form was a Likert scale with five answer options, namely "Strongly Disagree," "Disagree," "Neutral," "Agree," and "Strongly Agree."

Results

Table 1: Respondents' Demographical Data

SN	Data (N =60)		Frequency	Percent (%)
1	Age (According to Depkes, 2020)	Early Adult 26-35 years old	44	73,3
		Late Adult 36-45 years old	16	26,7
		Total	60	100.0
2	Gender	Male	15	25
		Female	45	75
		Total	60	100.0
3	Marital Status	Single	13	21,7
		Married	47	78,3
		Total	60	100.0
4	Room	Arafah	10	16,7
		Azahra	9	15
		Humaira	13	21,7
		Marwah	13	21,7
		Raudhah	15	25
		Total	60	100.0
5	Last Education	Associate`s Degree (D3)	12	71,7
		Associate`s Degree (D4)	1	1,7
		Bachelor	16	26,6
		Total	60	100.0

Table 1 show that most respondents are in the early adult category (26-35 years), 44 respondents (73.3%). For gender, the most dominant respondents are female as many as 45 respondents (75%). Then, most respondents were married to 47 respondents (78.3%). In addition, the majority of respondents were in the Raudhah room with 15 respondents (25.0%), and finally, the most recent education was diploma (D3) as many as 43 respondents (71.7%).

Table 2. Implementation of Organizational Culture in Inpatient Rooms at Banda Aceh

SN	Variable (N =60)		Frequency	Percent (%)
1	Organizational Culture	Deficient	23	38.3
		Good	37	61.7
		Total	60	100.0
Sub Variable				
2	Involvement	Deficient	19	31.7

		Good	41	68.3
		Total	60	100.0
3	Consistency	Deficient	21	35.0
		Good	39	65.0
		Total	60	100.0
4	Adjustment	Deficient	18	30.0
		Good	42	70.0
		Total	60	100.0
5	Mission	Deficient	23	38.3
		Good	37	61.7
		Total	60	100.0

Based on table 2, it can be explained that most of the respondents have a good level of perception of organizational culture were 37 respondents (61.7%). In the involvement, 41 respondents (68.3%) were in a good category. Then, 39 respondents (65%) were in the good category for consistency, followed by 42 respondents (70%) who were in a good category in the adjustment sub-variable. Finally, 37 respondents (61.7%) were in a good category.

Discussion

The results showed that most nurses in the inpatient room at the Banda Aceh hospital perceived a good organizational culture, with 37 respondents (61.7%). It also indicated that the dimension of involvement in this study is a value of the organization, emphasizing the importance of nurses who work together to achieve organizational goals (Harahap, 2018). Based on the results of univariate analysis, most head nurses perceived good involvement in a total of 41 respondents (68.3%). The results of this study are compatible with the research conducted by Kalsum et al. (2017), which stated that a high level of involvement and participation would create a sense of ownership and responsibility so that nurses' increased commitment to the organization is obtained.

The high involvement of head nurses in teamwork within the organization will increase nurse performance. This situation needs to be realized by the head of the room to allow the nurses to be involved in activities in the hospital, especially those related to nursing services.

The study results also showed that most head nurses perceived good consistency of organizational culture with 39 respondents (65.0%). Consistency in this study describes the nurse's assessment of the hospital organization's values related to applying hospital values, the accuracy of implementing nursing care, and the agreement. Good consistency will impact nurses' performance in providing nursing care services to patients.

According to Denison (2011), nurses' consistency in implementing work procedures and leadership in applying applicable rules must create a strong culture. Head nurses with a firm consistency will always orient on the overall values in carrying out their duties and providing services to the community, fulfill control and

evaluation of performance, and try to create things that can improve performance effectively.

The results explained that most head nurses perceived good compliance, as many as 42 respondents (70.0%). This result is in line with the opinion of Marquis and Hoston (2017) stated that the unit of the organization has a culture. The adjustment will occur if the unit's culture is parallel with the organizational culture and nursing culture is similar to other professional cultures. However, if it is the opposite, there will be inequality, which will impact the motivation and performance of nurses.

The results also showed that 37 respondents (61.7%) perceived the mission of the organizational culture with good results. This result means that nurses already understand the vision and mission of the hospital in providing nursing services in the inpatient room at the Banda Aceh hospital. The overall mission indicators in this study indicate that the implementing nurse makes the mission the primary basis for the quality of nursing service implementation.

According to Denison (2000), characteristics of the mission include organizational goals, vision, and achievement of organizational goals. Organizations that have a clear and well-directed mission through organizational goals will provide work motivation for nurses to improve nurses' performances.

The mission presented by the Meuraxa General Hospital is to provide professional and Islamic services, to improve hospital facilities and infrastructure, to improve the quality and welfare of human resources, and to create a healthy and Islamic working environment and culture.

This study showed that the majority of respondents were in early adulthood, with 44 respondents (73.3%), similar to Sari's research (2019) which stated that nurses who are mature and productive have more competence, skills, and maturity in providing nursing services and have a high commitment to the quality of services offered.

In addition, the results of the study also proved that most of the nurses in the inpatient room at Banda Aceh hospital had an Associate's Degree (three to four years diploma) in nursing education. The level of education can improve nurses' ability in terms of intellectual, technical and interpersonal needed in carrying out nursing care. This statement follows the opinion of Blundel et al. (1999) in (Lapau et al., 2021), which stated that the level of education would be beneficial for many organizations, the level of education is a prerequisite for organizations in conducting recruitment.

Based on the study results and some of the opinions stated before, from the four dimensions of organizational culture (involvement, consistency, adjustment, and mission), most of the head nurses perceive it nicely (61.7%). This finding means that the organizational culture in the hospital inpatient room has been implemented and is expected to be maintained by nurses to create quality services.

Some activities that must be considered to improve the quality of hospital services are by increasing the dimensions of nurse involvement in every planning of nursing actions that will be given. Nurses' consistency in doing work correctly and adequately, nurses' ability to adapt according to the times and technology, and the

mission dimension must be considered to improve the quality of hospital nursing services.

Kholifah (2013) explained that the perception of organizational culture in Ambarawa Hospital indicated good performance related to organizational goals and reflected in the values applied when providing nursing care to patients.

This study also explained that most head nurses in every inpatient room at Banda Aceh Hospital had succeeded in carrying out the organizational culture. Similar to the opinion of Robbins and Timothy in Taurisa and Ratnawati (2012), organizational culture represents a common perception of organizational members who have different backgrounds and levels.

This study explains that every member of the organization in the inpatient room already understands the organizational culture with the same level of understanding.

Conclusion

Based on the research results from 60 respondents, the nurses' perceptions of organizational culture in the inpatient room at the Banda Aceh Hospital were in the right category at 37 respondents (61.7%) and the low category at 23 respondents (38.3%). It is hoped that the head of the inpatient ward will continue to improve the organizational culture of the hospital, as this will impact the performance of the head nurse.

Acknowledgment: Thanks to FON-USK for facilitating the implementation of this research. Also, Meuraxa Hospital Banda Aceh permitted this research to be carried out correctly.

Conflict of Interest: The researchers stated that there was no conflict of interest whatsoever in this study.

Source of Funding: None

References

- Ariani, A. P. (2016). *The Influence of Organizational Culture on Organizational Citizenship Behavior by Mediating Affective Commitment at the Regional Secretariat of Bandung Regency* [in Indonesian]. Tesis: Universitas Udayana Denpasar.
- Apriyatmoko, R., and Susilo, E. (2014). Budaya Organization and Professionalism of Nurses at Private Hospitals in Temanggung [in Indonesian]. *Jurnal Manajemen Keperawatan*. 2(2).
- Denison, C. (2011). Denison Overview: *Introduction to the Denison Model*. Ann Arbor, MI: Author.

- Fadhila, R., and Afriani, T. (2020). Application of Telenursing in Health Services: Literature Review [in Indonesian]. *Jurnal Keperawatan Abdurrah*, 3(2), 77-84.
- Kalsum, U., Ahmad, L. O. A. I., and Andisiri, W. O. S. N. (2017). The Influence of Organizational Culture on the Performance of Implementing Nurses in the Inpatient Room of Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2016 [in Indonesian]. *JIMKESMAS*, 2(6), 1-9.
- Harahap, S. Y. (2018). *Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi dan Penerapan Standar Asuhan Keperawatan terhadap Kinerja Perawat di Ruang Rawat Inap RS. Martha Friska Brayon Medan*. Tesis: Universitas Sumatera Utara.
- Kholifah, S. (2013). The Relationship between Organizational Culture Implementation and Patient Satisfaction at Abarawa Hospital [in Indonesian]. *Jurnal Manajemen Keperawatan*, 1(1), 7-14.
- Lapau, F., Shaleha, W. M., and Hakim, A. A. A. A. (2021). The Effect of Education Level, Training and Organizational Culture on the Performance of Bhayangkara Kendari Hospital Employees [in Indonesian]. *Jurnal Ilmiah Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Folres*, 11(1), 114-133.
- Permenkes RI. (2020). *Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia No. 80 of 2020 concerning the Hospital Quality Committee* [in Indonesian]. Jakarta: Menkes RI.
- Simamora, R., Bukit, E., and Siahaan, J. (2017). The influence of nurses' performance in providing nursing care through nursing round training at the Royal Prima Hospital Medan. [in Indonesian]. *Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 23(2).
- Sari, M. T., (2019). Perceptions of implementing nurses about organizational culture. [in Indonesian]. *Jurnal ilmiah Universitas Batanghari Jambi*, 8(1).
- Taurisa, C. M., and Ratnawati, I. (2012). Analysis of the Effect of Organizational Culture and Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment in Improving Employee Performance. [in Indonesian]. *Jurnal Bisnis dan Ekonomi*.

Cite this article:

Author(s), Usi Retno Zulyanty, Ns. Andara Maurissa, MNS, Ns. Mayanti Mahdarsari, S.Kep., M.Kep, Ns. Ardia Putra MNS, AND Ns. Yuswardi, MNS, (2021). "Nurse's Perceived on the Head Nurse Organizational Culture in Inpatient Room of Banda Aceh Hospital", **Name of the Journal**: International Journal of Medicine, Nursing & Health Sciences, (IJMNHS.COM), P, 86 – 94. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5810351 , Issue: 6, Vol.: 2, Article: 8, Month: December, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijmnhs.com/all-issues/>

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